

28-30 SEPTEMBER 2022

TOWARD AN ON-BOARD AI PROOF OF CONCEPT FOR CHIME: A FEASIBILITY STUDY

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INTRODUCTION

The Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) aims to augment the Copernicus space component thanks to precise spectroscopic measurements with 250 spectral channels within the 400-2500 nm wavelengths range on a 130 km on ground swath at 30 m Spatial Sampling Distance (at equator). CHIME will support the monitoring, implementation and improvement of a range of policies related to food security and agriculture, soils, raw materials, biodiversity, environmental hazards, inland and coastal waters, snow, forestry and the urban environment.

CHIME will produce a near-continuous stream of high-dimensional data resulting in unprecedented data volumes. This calls for fast and computationally efficient methods for the storage, transmission and analysis of the data. As a complementary tool, on-board Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds special promise for hyperspectral missions such as CHIME: processing the data on-board a satellite can reduce the time and cost of data transfer and processing, enabling to send only the most valuable insights to the ground, and focusing on rapid responses to events and detected phenomena that impact our society and require fast decision-making. Another interest would also be in the data collection outside of the mission baseline scenario, as far as an event is identified by an on-board AI unit. Given that the power of hyperspectral EO lies in its capability to simultaneously detect spectral signatures within a wide range of applications, and related policy areas, on-board AI has huge potential for autonomous tasking and detection of many events and/or phenomena, thus the spacecraft itself can recognize multiple targets of opportunity and trigger the needed response actions in a fast and efficient manner. ESA and Thales Alenia Space as industrial responsible of the satellite are currently identifying potential applications and further study the feasibility of a proof of concept that may be on-board the mission and corresponding constraints. This study is being led in partnership with KP Labs for AI expertise and algorithm developments and KILI technologies for data collection and annotation. The working group objective is to identify new potential use cases suitable for AI processing on-board (e.g., rapid response and environmental awareness, for fast decision-making or extension of the mission perimeter).

This paper presents the study main outputs concerning applications identified valuable for the CHIME mission and discuss the problematic of including AI function in CHIME nominal acquisition data chain. Through a proposed detailed use case of methane super emitter detection, the data maturity subject is evocated, as most of the data which is available on ground is calibrated and corrected and may have poor representativeness of what is expected while in orbit.

TOWARD AI ON BOARD CHIME: MOTIVATION AND SELECTION OF TARGET AI APPLICATION

Core mission coverage and nominal acquisition logic

The main mission objective of the Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission is: “To provide routine hyperspectral observations through the Copernicus Programme in support of EU and related policies for the management of natural resources, assets and benefits. This unique visible-to-shortwave infra-red spectroscopy based observational capability will in particular support new and enhanced services for food security, agriculture and raw materials. This includes sustainable agricultural and biodiversity management, soil properties characterization, sustainable mining practices and environment preservation.” [1]. To this aim, continuous acquisitions are performed between -56 and + 75 degrees latitudes on emerged areas, coastal areas and open water (wherever the depth does not exceed 50m). Such nominal acquisition coverage considered as “core mission coverage” is illustrated in Fig. 1. A swath of 130km with SSD of 30m requires then at least 4500 pixels across track.

Fig. 1. CHIME core mission coverage : dark green areas corresponds to land coverage, light green corresponds to coastal areas

Performances for the monitoring of hyperspectral domain require 250 spectral bands between 400 and 2500nm with a spectral resolution less or equal to 10nm. An instrument throughput of typically 4.5Gbps is so expected in nominal acquisition mode on the core mission coverage. This data rate and the amount of data to be collected during the mission made then necessary the use of an optimized compression solution on board to cope both with mass memory volume limitation and even downlink capacity bottleneck (up to 3.7Gbps on a single polarization Ka band link). It also brings an additional positive effect in the form of tremendous reduction of the operational costs linked to the data delivery to the ground.

A CHIME Data Processing Unit (DPU) is so developed for hyperspectral selective compression that enables tunable losses separately on cloudy areas and on “useful” land data in the image. A first AI-assisted approach is used via a cloud detection algorithm using a SVM approach on-board for which the parameters are optimized through on-ground supervised learning techniques using annotated cloudy hyperspectral images [2]. The DPU processes the whole hyperspectral data in real time for collection of compressed hyperspectral data in dedicated files. A square image of 130km x 130km is estimated to 75Gbits of uncompressed data and a compression ratio of typically 4 is expected during the mission.

This onboard data processing architecture allows together with the Hyperspectral Imager (HSI) to acquire data with high spectral, spatial and radiometric quality. This data will have the potential to deliver significant enhancement in quantitative value-added products as required in the Mission Requirement Document [1]. Apart from this, an enhancement of the Onboard processing capability is currently assessed by the team and some initial results are reported in the following sections.

Inclusion of AI function and corresponding data processing approach

As illustrated on Fig. 2, including an AI function in CHIME data processing implies for the DPU to relay in an uncompressed format part of the spectrum that may be useful for an AI diagnostic computed on an AI routine operating on the data extract. Table 1 lists a subset of AI applications on hyperspectral data investigated in the literature. A more exhaustive study has been performed by our team and relayed in [3].

Table 1 Potential on board AI use cases and corresponding wavelengths of interest

	Wavelengths of interest (nm)	Estimated number of bands for data extraction on CHIME	Reference
Volcanic ash clouds	400 – 600	21	[4]
Landslides	450-510; 520-580; 655-690; 780 – 920	34	[5]
Methane plumes	1600 – 2500	91	[6]
Plastic in oceans	800 – 1900	111	[7]

The onboard AI function shall work not only on a subset of spectral bands but also on a limited number of pixels at a time considering a patch approach that would be also used for on ground trainings before the corresponding resulting network is uploaded on board. Considering 64x64 pixels typical dimensions, the AI function shall be able to process typically 4584 patches to cover the full square image of 130km x 130km (data rates depending on numbers of spectral bands retained among the 250 delivered by the instrument).

Fig. 2. Data acquisition and processing logic on CHIME

Moving from a core mission approach assuring hyper spectral image integrity and completeness with tailored compression to an AI function operating on patches performing on-board diagnostic by classifying, detecting or segmenting patch information led us on three possible interests for AI on board:

1. Sending an ‘alert’ delivering an information to end users through a dedicated communication channel sooner than CHIME expected data latency between 5 to 12 hours after acquisition time (for a Level 2a product): this possibility would apply for missions hosting fast and reactive communication channel towards disseminated end users, but not for CHIME Ka band downlink data chain being sized for massive data download on ESA ground stations.
2. Extending the mission coverage by making instrument acquisitions beyond the core mission coverage and asking AI to retain only the most valuable information to cope with limited memory storage and downloadable data volume margins. This latter possibility of “intelligent” complementary acquisitions may concentrate on ‘anomalies’ identified among ocean areas with:
 - a. classification of patches for applications that may imply a characterization with information level as concentrations estimations that goes above the estimation of presence or absence and that calls for quantification(s) (plastic litter, algae blooms, oil spills, ...)
 - b. detection of objects compatible with CHIME SSD of 30m (boats, watercrafts, containers, ...)

Even if not illustrated in a use case in this communication, this use of AI function on board may allow CHIME to cover oceanic areas only retaining singularities to be transmitted in the same time as core mission information.

3. Triggering a response from one satellite by information extracted of patch(es) like complementary acquisition(s) or information relay to another satellite without the involvement of operations management on ground. This automated operations functionality is applicable for multi-instrument missions or missions with existing links between satellites. For CHIME this capability cannot be made use of due to the existing mission baseline scenario not foreseeing satellite inter-links.

To illustrate the first scenario, which appeared compatible with CHIME at the time of the study and taking benefit of information contained in collected HS material, a methane detection is considered as studied use case in the next section of this paper. The goal being to identify methane super emitters on ground. The reason justifying such use case has been both strong interest of the community on this subject and the availability of hyper spectral data from AVIRIS NG that allowed emulation of CHIME acquisitions scenario. Next section shows that methane sources can be identified with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) applied to HS collected material and complementary methane concentration map computed from it.

METHANE DETECTION FROM HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGES: EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Related Work

Methane (CH_4) is an example of one of the most important greenhouse gases with a strong climate impact [8]. It has 28 times greater global warming potential than carbon dioxide (CO_2), due to its significant impact on the global radiation balance [9]. This phenomenon causes changes in ecosystems, which can be estimated by determining the value of the concentration of methane [10]. Over the years, an increase in the concentration of methane in the atmosphere has been observed, both from natural [10] as well as anthropogenic sources [11] such as industry [8, 12], agriculture [13, 14] or landfill [15]. The detection, monitoring and prediction of methane sources can form the basis for managing and responding to anthropogenic sources to reduce emissions of this greenhouse gas and stem climate change [9] or use the waste sector, which is responsible for 16% of emissions [16] as an inexpensive source of energy [15].

The mapping of CH_4 sources is carried out using multispectral images (MSIs) and hyperspectral images (HSIs) acquired both by terrestrial and satellite methods. Reference data can be obtained by in-situ measurements [10] or are obtained with reference to manually annotated data from the Sentinel-5P methane product [17, 18]. There have been several approaches proposed so far to detect methane plumes from hyperspectral imagery. Beside making use of physical-based algorithms, Kumar et al. [19] suggested to perform initial matched filtering of the input image to extract initial methane concentration maps which are further processed (together with the input hyperspectral data) using a deep learning-powered object detector [19]. For the retrieval of Methane Super Emitters, it was shown recently, that the use solely the SWIR spectral range of the spectrum may be sufficient [20]. Using the data of Gaofen-5 and PRISMA sensors, the wavelength range from 2000 to 2500 nm corresponds to water vapor, carbon dioxide and methane. Here, the window from 2100 to 2450 nm is especially sensitive to methane [20]. A similar range is observed for the multispectral Sentinel-2 sensor, for which strong absorption lines corresponding to methane are visible in band 12 (2090-2290 nm). Poor characteristics of the spectral signature were also noted in this case for the band 11 (1560-1660 nm). Hyperspectral sensors such as Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer-New Generation (AVIRIS-NG) and Shortwave Airborne Spectrographic Imager (SASI) are also effective gas observation tools due to their spectral range [19, 8]. In the first case, the bands corresponding to the range of 2200 nm to 2500 nm should be analyzed [19], whereas in the second, strong absorption is visible between 2200 nm and 2400 nm and weak at nearly 1674 nm [15]. Nevertheless, the low spatial resolution of this satellite limits its effectiveness, so an approach was taken that fused Landsat-8 images with Sentinel-2 images, which have higher spatial resolution, thus enables a more favorable greenhouse gas mapping [15, 21].

The AI approaches toward detecting methane from satellite image data span across both classic and deep machine learning techniques, with the latter benefiting from automated representation learning (they do not require designing hand-crafted feature extractors, as they are learned during the training process). Although classic random forests were utilized for this task [10], convolutional neural networks (CNN), like fully-convolutional U-Nets [21] or hyperspectral Mask-RCNNs [19] established the current state of the art in the field. In this paper, we exploit a CNN [22] to delineate methane plumes from hyperspectral data acquired using the AVIRIS sensor in a pixel-wise manner. Also, we investigate the capabilities of the CNN over the CHIME-like data, which is the resampled version of the AVIRIS images that better reflects the expected characteristics of the hyperspectral images captured by the CHIME sensor [23]. The resampling process is rendered in Fig. 3 – the original AVIRIS-NG data (varying spatial resolution, 432 bands with 5 nm spectral resolution) is spectrally and spatially resampled to match the resolution of CHIME data (30 m spatial resolution, 250 bands with ≤ 10 nm spectral resolution). After the resampling process, we generated CHIME-like patches of 64×64 pixels with 250 spectral bands.

Fig. 3. The process of simulating CHIME-like data from AVIRIS-NG imagery.

Methane Detection from AVIRIS and CHIME-like Hyperspectral Data Using a CNN

To detect methane from hyperspectral image data, we exploited a CNN encompassing three 2D convolutional layers with 16, 32, and 64 kernels (3×3) acting as a feature extractor and followed by a Dice pixel classification layer. The generalized Dice coefficient quantifies the overlap between two images, e.g., segmented methane areas and the corresponding ground-truth methane areas (the perfect overlap is quantified as the Dice score of one). This network operates on selected bands from the full hyperspectral data, and on the methane concentration map extracted using the approach suggested by Thompson et al. [24]. The network was trained separately over each fold for 30 epochs with generalized Dice loss utilized as a loss function. We followed a four-fold cross-validation procedure over the Methane Benchmark Dataset [25] containing 16 methane patches extracted from the hyperspectral images acquired by nine flights. It is of note that this data is extremely imbalanced – in the patches included in folds 1-4, only 15%, 5%, 1%, and 1% of all pixels constitute methane.

To quantify the segmentation quality, we exploit classic overlap metrics, being the Dice and the Jaccard's indices (the latter often referred to as the Intersection over Union, IoU), with the latter metric penalizing single instances of bad segmentation more than Dice. The metrics are given as $Dice = 2TP / (2TP + FP + FN)$ and $IoU = TP / (TP + FP + FN)$, where TP, TN, FP and FN are true positives (methane pixels correctly determined by a deep learning model), true negatives (background pixels correctly determined by a model), false positives (background pixels incorrectly annotated as methane) and false negatives (methane pixels incorrectly classified as background), respectively. The CNN operating on the R, G, B channel together with the two normalized versions of the CH_4 concentration maps (we followed the local and global normalization, as suggested by Kumar et al. [19]) elaborated the mean (median) Dice of 0.30 (0.26), and the mean (median) IoU of 0.18 (0.13). Although those values could be considered rather low for a segmentation task (both metrics should be maximized, and 1.0 corresponds to the perfect segmentation in both cases), the qualitative analysis (Fig. 4a) shows that our CNN is able to correctly *detect* methane super emitters, and the predicted (binary) methane maps are consistent with the corresponding CH_4 retrievals (which are not binarized) available as the ground truth. Therefore, the overlap metrics should be interpreted with care, as they may lead to inferring over-pessimistic conclusions about the performance of the segmentation algorithm, as they are bounded by the quality of the ground-truth binary masks. This observation is further manifested in Fig. 4c – although the binary mask indeed presents a methane super emitter, there are other areas containing methane-like pixels (pointed out by the black arrows). Such areas which might be presenting methane (of lower concentration) were not included in the binary ground-truth masks, hence they directly affect the overlap metrics. Additionally, utilizing such lower-intensity areas during the training process could serve as an additional regularization – this, however, requires further investigation. Interestingly, performing the inference over the CHIME-like data led to obtaining consistent results when compared with those elaborated for the AVIRIS-NG patches (Fig. 4b). The two-tailed Wilcoxon signed-rank tests showed that deploying our CNNs over the AVIRIS-NG and CHIME-like patches resulted in the statistically the same Dice and IoU scores (at $p < 0.05$). Overall, our experimental study performed over airborne AVIRIS-NG and simulated CHIME-like data show that it is possible to detect methane from HSI using a fairly simple CNN (thus easy to deploy in constrained execution environments) still with the support of pre calculated concentration map.

c) An example AVIRIS-NG patch with the overlaid binary ground-truth methane mask (in red), together with the corresponding CH₄ retrievals also available in the Methane Benchmark Dataset

Fig. 4. Example segmentation obtained using our CNN over a) the original AVIRIS-NG test patch, and the corresponding b) CHIME-like test patch (after the resampling process). In c), we present an example ground-truth patch with the binary methane mask (in red), together with the corresponding (non-binarized) CH₄ retrievals, also available in the Methane Benchmark Dataset [25]. The black arrows indicate methane-like pixels which are not captured in binary methane masks. Images in graphics show patches cut from hyperspectral images of whole AVIRIS-NG flight.

CONCLUSIONS

CHIME will provide an enhanced hyperspectral data acquisition capabilities when compared to the precursor missions such as EnMAP (DLR) and PRISMA (ASI). This enhanced capability is realised using onboard data processing capabilities. In a currently ongoing feasibility study further advances of onboard processing is studying taking into account deep learning capabilities for solving a variety of Earth observation tasks through object detection, image classification or semantic segmentation of hyperspectral data, ESA is currently targeting the objective to identify new use cases that would be relevant for AI applications on-board CHIME. Right now, the decision to implement a dedicated Artificial Intelligence Unit (AIU) on-board CHIME is still pending; however, to tackle these technological and operational challenges, ESA and Thales Alenia Space, with the partnership of KP Labs and KILI technologies are assessing the potential enhancement of the CHIME on-board processing capabilities with AI.

AI on-board CHIME may bring new capabilities at satellite, system and mission levels such as (i) extend the mission perimeter out of the initial core mission, (ii) improve on-board data selection, reduction or compression, (iii) increase the on-board to on-ground image chain reactivity. Here, we demonstrate the ability to detect methane emitters using matched filter and deep-learning techniques applied on hyperspectral CHIME-like data simulated from AVIRIS-NG scenes. Since this approach involves performing matched filtering, we are currently working on the patch classification approaches (to not delineate the methane areas, but to classify the image as containing or non-containing any methane pixels) operating on the hyperspectral data only. This would allow for further acceleration of the on-board processing chain, and would be a step toward the smart compression pipeline. Here, such patches which do contain methane could be signaled and / or downlinked to the ground for further analysis, e.g., for the precision delineation of methane areas.

The implementation of deep-learning models in the AIU imposes new constraints on the architecture of the current on-board data processing chain as well as strong challenges on the hardware of AIU, such as high speed I/O memory links, fast data processing cores, parallelization of data processing units. The main challenge for the AIU is to ensure a continuous processing imposed by the push-broom data acquisition principle alongside the constant monitoring requirement of the CHIME mission. This may have further impacts at algorithm level so that the AIU design shall take into account algorithm performances and robustness, but also the difficulty to design the training and test databases, the complexity to implement the solution on the hardware target as well as the impact on satellite and system architecture including the memory requirements, function re-configurability, power consumption, mass, volume and radiations tolerance. Then, the final decision to implement an AIU on-board CHIME and the selection of the application cases will result from an overall trade-off showing that AI on-board not only provides an operational added value in terms of performance, reactivity, autonomy or extended capacities, but also from the engineering, industrial, operational, commercial and scientific points of view on how it may benefit to the companies developing the solution, the customer or the agency owning and operating the system and ultimately the end user exploiting the data.

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